

199°–200°, 204⁵, 205⁴, 212¹) (Found : C, 68.2; H, 4.9; Calculated for C₁₇H₁₄O₅ : C, 68.4 and H, 4.7).

Partial decarboxylation of (IV) to give (III): The 4-carboxy-isocoumarin (IV) (0.5 g.) was heated at 220° in a metal bath for 5 min. (evolution of CO₂). The contents, after cooling were repeatedly extracted with ether. Removal of ether from the extract gave a solid that crystallised from dilute methanol as silky needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen 206°–7°.

The ester (V)-esterification of (III) with MeOH/H₂SO₄: The isocoumarin (III) (0.5 g.), methanol (30 ml.) and H₂SO₄ (1 ml.) were mixed and refluxed for 2 hr. Methanol (15 ml.) was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water (80 ml.). The sticky product was taken in ether, washed with aq. NaHCO₃. Removal of ether from the extract gave a solid that crystallised from *n*-hexane as colourless needles, m.p. 106°–7° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 107°–9°) (Found : C, 73.7; H, 4.9. C₁₈H₁₅O₄ requires : C, 73.5 and H, 4.76%).

3-(2-Carboxybenzyl)-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIII)-Reduction of (VI) with NaBH₄: To the ethanolic solution of the ketone (VI) (0.5 g. in 15 ml.), NaBH₄ (0.37 g.) was added in small portions with shaking and the mixture was left aside for 2 hr at room temperature. Crushed ice and conc. HCl were added with stirring till the metallic chlorides dissolved to give a turbid solution that gave a solid on scratching. It crystallised from benzene as clusters of small needles, m.p. 183°–5° (decomp.), yield 0.42 g.

(Lit.¹ m.p. 186°) (Found : C, 72.4; H, 5.2; C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires : C, 72.4 and H, 4.9%), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 232, 280 nm (log ϵ 4.12 and 3.24).

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A Note on the Cobalt (II) Chelate of 2,3-dioxo-butyranilide 2-oxime

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RECENTLY, Pathak and Haldar¹ considered the preparation of orange red tris(isonitroso acetophenonato) cobalt(III) from cobalt(II) and isonitroso acetophenone, and observed that it is diamagnetic and its d-d bands are masked by the presence of high intensity pi-pi and charge transfer bands.

We report here briefly our findings on the cobalt (II) chelate of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime. It is orange-red in colour and is formulated as HCoL_3 . It is paramagnetic and its magnetic moment at room temperature is found to be 1.86 B.M. It shows the presence of one unpaired electron and hence of bivalent cobalt. The octahedral crystal field is considered to be strong leading to the spin-pairing of d-electrons in cobalt (II). The visible absorption spectrum of the chelate has a d-d band at 17000 cm^{-1} . The band is attributed to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. in the strong octahedral crystal field. The crystal field splitting (Δ) is suggested to be 17000 cm^{-1} . Usually, the spin-pairing energy (P) for cobalt (II) in its weak octahedral complexes is given as $\sim 22500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Δ as $\sim 10000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Since p will be higher than Δ , no spin-pairing should be observed in such complexes. We find that covalent bonding, as evidenced by the determination of β , is present to a considerable extent in the chelate. Hence spin-pairing energy which can be evaluated as $4B+4C$ (where B and C are Racah parameters) has been found to have a low value of 12240 cm^{-1} . It indicates favourable condition ($\Delta > p$) for spin-pairing in the chelate. Further, from the comparative studies of other chelates, it is considered likely that pi-bonding between metal and ligand exists. It would involve t_{2g} electrons of cobalt (II) leading to the delocalisation of these electrons (i.e., apparently modifying the bivalent nature of cobalt).

Reference

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Outer Sphere Association in Tris(biguanide) Cobalt (III) Salts

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TRIS(BIGUANIDE) cobalt (III) cation has a high inner sphere formation constant¹ ($K = 10^{54}$). The complex shows asymmetric transformation of the second order during resolution². Furthermore the complex also shows interesting kinetics and mechanistic behaviour during acid hydrolysis³. We now report the outer sphere association constants of the salts $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$ (BigH = biguanide; X = Cl, Br, I, and $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$)

The association constants were obtained from a study of the conductance of the pure salts with dilution in aqueous medium at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. An approximate value of Λ^0 was obtained by plotting the experimental Λ against $\sqrt{c}$. The approximate

Λ^0 was fitted into Onsager's conductivity equation⁴ and 'b' value was thus obtained. From a plot of $\Lambda + b\sqrt{c}$ against c an accurate value of the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution, Λ^0 (Onsager), was obtained whence Λ^0_i , the limiting conductivity of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$, was available. The experimental conductivity plots lie below the Onsager plots, which is taken to mean that outer sphere association occurs in these salts. Table 1, gives the values of Λ^0 , Λ^0 (Onsager) and Λ^0_i for the chloride, bromide and the iodide salts of the complex cation.

Assuming the ion-pair to be $\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2\text{X}]\text{X}_2$ (X = Cl, Br, I), Onsager equations for the 3:1 valent salt ($[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$) and for the 2:1 salt (the ion-pair) have been written. and association constants for the equilibrium

have been calculated following Jenkins and Monk⁵. For the sulphate salt Λ^0 (Onsager) was obtained by adding 80.00 for the sulphate ion to the mean limiting cation conductivity derived from the chloride, bromide and iodide salts. The outer sphere association constants are given in Table 2. Comparison of these constants with those of $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ and $\{[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (en = ethylenediamine; X = Cl, Br, I, SO_4) shows that, the constants increase in the usual order $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE DATA OF $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$ (X = Cl, Br, I) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$

Complex salt	Approximate Λ^0	Onsager Λ^0	Λ^0_i (for the cation)	Mean Λ^0_i
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	146.00	143.88	67.54	
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Br}_3$	148.00	147.00	68.60	68.08
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{I}_3$	145.00	144.90	68.10	

TABLE 2—OUTER SPHERE ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3\text{X}_2]\text{X}_2$

Ion-pair	Association constant
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{Cl}]\}^{2+}$	55
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{Br}]\}^{2+}$	33
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{I}]\}^{2+}$	22
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{SO}_4)\}^{2+}$	16×10^2

From a knowledge of the limiting conductivity of the ion, the ionic radius has been calculated from Stoke's law (Table 3). Expectedly $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ (1.03 Å) is substantially bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ (2.77 Å)⁶ and is only slightly bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ (3.68 Å)⁵. A smaller value compared to the size⁶